

Needs and expectations regarding agroforestry tree management: A survey of the French stakeholder Network

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Despite evidence of the many benefits associated with the presence of trees in agricultural environments, agroforestry is struggling to spread widely in Europe. Given that the agricultural sector is making increasing use of digital technologies to improve its performance, and that the development of digital tools for agroforestry is still in its infancy, the aim of the European research project DIGITAF (DIGItal Tools to boost AgroForestry) is to develop tools and models that meet users' needs for the development of agroforestry.

In this context, UMR AMAP is responsible for evaluating tree management tools and identifying potential levers for improving these tools, based on its expertise in plant architecture (Barthélémy and Caraglio 2007). Architectural analysis is a remarkable diagnostic tool, because disorders in tree functioning are often manifested by a disorganisation of its architecture. This approach allows to determine the current state and potential of a tree by combining the observation of different types of markers: architectural development markers for defining its stage of development, growth markers for providing information about its vitality and reaction markers for characterizing its response to its environment and any disturbances. The architectural diagnosis approach has already contributed to forest management by proposing different types of tools to diagnose trees and assess their reactivity to environmental disturbances (Drénou 2013; Sabatier et al. 2014). The aim here is to assess the contribution of the architectural approach in an agroforestry context to improving tree management practices.

We have previously identified several situations in which the architectural approach can be applied:

- diagnosis of seedlings before planting to help with seedling selection, or even to improve nursery growing methods,
- Diagnosis of recovery in the first few years after planting (Figure 1), to help monitor plantations,
- diagnosis of trees installed following a recent planting, to help in the decision-making process for pruning operations and for the reorientation of poorly conformed trees.

Figure 1 The location and strength of growth (in green) and the reaction (in red) are good indicators of tree regrowth

An initial survey of participants in the six Living Labs of the DIGITAF project showed that the lack of knowledge about tree management and performance was a major problem identified in four Living

Labs (Table 1). However, the tool needs that emerge most strongly from the survey are design tools (6 Living Labs), species/variety selection tools (6 Living Labs) and tree performance prediction tools (5 Living Labs). The need for tree management tools is less widespread, and relates more specifically to tree pruning (3 Living Labs) and tree health diagnostics (2 Living Labs).

Table 1 Results from the Living Labs survey summaries - selection of questions relating to tree management (DIGITAF - deliverables D2.1 and D4.1). X's indicate that the answer has been ticked at least once.

	Czech R.	Finland	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	UK
Answers	20	3	12 (10 LL)	12	14	8
- Farmers	11	2	6	3	5	2
- Advisors		-		5	3	-
Problematic aspects for the development of agroforestry potentially linked to tree management						
Lack of technical knowledge of AFS	X	X		X	X	
Complexity of AFS		X		X	X	X
Lack of knowledge about tree management/performance	X	X		X	X	X
Lack of knowledge about interactions with livestock						X
Needs regarding tree management						
Tools for design	X	X	X	X	X	X
Tools for species selection	X	X	X	X	X	X
Tools for tree management :	X	X		X	X	
- pruning		X		X	X	
- health / care diagnosis				X	X	
- productivity optimisation					X	
Tree performance prediction :	X	X		X	X	X
- fodder production					X	
Forecasting, monitoring and management					X	
Economic performance prediction				X	X	
Monitoring/predicting the costs and benefits of AFS					X	
Monitoring/prediction of carbon storage		X		X		X
Types of tools (all needs combined, not specific to tree management)						
Media for disseminating knowledge				X	X	
Decision-making tools	X	X	X		X	
Visualisation tools at plot and landscape level :		X			X	
- visualisation of tree crown development		X				
Collaborative tool: sharing knowledge and best practices			X		X	X
Tools for teaching		X				

On the basis of these initial results, we wanted to identify the existing tools, their possible limitations, and how the architectural approach could make an effective contribution to tree management. We started by establishing a diagnosis of the current situation in France by combining elements from the literature and from an inventory of available tools. We then conducted a series of semi-structured interviews with twelve stakeholders in the development of agroforestry in France (Table 2) in order to clarify the issues and expectations of stakeholders in the field with regard to tree management. We chose to contact advisors, technicians, trainers and researchers, on the assumption that this would enable us to summarise farmers' observations and needs at a local, regional or national level, depending on the role of the interviewee. The interviews, lasting between one and two hours, were

conducted by videoconference between October 2023 and February 2024. They were also used to complete the initial inventory of tree management tools.

Table 2 Structures interviewed, types of actions in agroforestry and geographical scope of action

Structure	Type	Geographical scope
AGROOF (2 interviewees)	Research / Training / Advice	Gard / Hérault / France
Afac-Agroforesteries	Network structuring	France
Arbres et Paysages 32	Advice / Training	Gers
Arbres, Haies, Paysages d'Aveyron	Advice / Training	Aveyron
Chambre d'agriculture - Ariège	Advice / Training	Ariège
Chambre d'Agriculture - Nord Pas de Calais	Advice / Training	Hauts de France
Chambre d'agriculture - Pays de la Loire	Advice / Training	Pays de la Loire / France
CNPF	Training	France
Envol vert	Advice / Training	Tarn
INRAE, DYNAFOR	Research	France
Silva Domestica	Advice	Normandie

A number of observations emerged from these interviews, which seem to be broadly shared by the various stakeholders interviewed:

1. In France, various players may be involved in the management of field trees and hedges, depending on the stage of management.

The stakeholders involved vary according to the management stage, the type of agroforestry formation and the associated production/service objectives, but also according to the local context (Table 3). For example, the existence of structured production chains and the availability of service providers and equipment for maintenance and operation also play a role in determining the stakeholders involved. But even without the existence of such networks, in certain regions we can observe an increase in the outsourcing of hedge maintenance and tree harvesting, accompanied by an increase in the mechanisation of these tasks.

Table 3 Involvement of the various stakeholders in the different agroforestry tree management operations. Occasional involvement is shown in light green and strong involvement in dark green.

	Farmers	Tree nurseries	Local advisory structures	Local authorities	Cuma*	SCIC** for wood-energy	service providers	Individuals
Design, species selection								
Management plan								
Production of seedlings								
Planting								
Recovery monitoring (~ 3 years)								
Mulching, watering, weeding...								
Pruning								
Hedge maintenance								
Fuelwood harvesting								
Wood chips harvesting								
Timber harvesting								

*Cooperative for the use of agricultural equipment, **Collective interest cooperative

Consequently, improving the management of field trees involves identifying all the players involved locally and mobilising them in ways that can be adapted to each situation.

2. The performance expected of trees relates more to ecological services than to production.

Most of the interviewees felt that farmers had a fairly good knowledge of the various services provided by trees. While all types of agroforestry are considered to provide several services, the hedgerow is presented as the tree formation that provides a whole range of services. Ecological services are cited more often than tree-related production, except in the case of orchards and forest gardens. In particular, timber production appears to be a very minor objective for recent plantations. Several interviewees emphasised that timber production is not restricted to intra-parcel alignments. For some, the excessive spacing of trees presents farmers with technical challenges that are too great for the production of quality timber, which contributes to the idea that timber production should be reserved for forests. They recommend that intra-parcel plantations be managed as hedgerows to facilitate timber production and improve the ecological services provided.

3. The management of existing trees is considered highly unsatisfactory and seems to compromise the expected ecosystem services in the case of hedges, and the timber production objectives where they exist.

While the planting stage is considered to be well mastered and giving satisfactory results, the management of the trees in place is considered to be very unsatisfactory. This observation was widely shared by the participants in the interviews and concerns all types of agroforestry, but for different reasons and therefore with different improvement issues. The first problem concerns hedgerows: current maintenance practices are considered to be incompatible with the maintenance of their good ecological status, and therefore with the provision of the ecosystem services that might be expected of them. A second problem is specific to the objective of producing timber, whether for trees planted in rows within plots or in hedgerows: the general lack of tree management in the first few years makes it impossible to produce quality timber. This lack of monitoring has also a non negligible effect on the integration of trees at farm level, as tree training is also essential to make their presence compatible with the passage of agricultural equipment. An exception seems to be the management of fruit trees.

The consequences of inappropriate management on the current performance of agroforestry systems at national level are difficult to assess. In the absence of long-term monitoring data on plantations and data aggregated at national level, it is difficult to assess the current performance of agroforestry systems in relation to their initial objectives. However, interviewees felt that for some services, the benefits of trees can be seen fairly quickly (erosion control, drainage, landscape, etc.).

4. The main obstacles to good tree management are the lack of knowledge about trees and the lack of available labour.

During the interviews, many different reasons were given to explain the lack of management or poor management of field trees and hedges. Among these, the most often cited reason was the lack of knowledge about trees on the part of the various stakeholders (farmers, advisers from support structures, local authorities, contractors). The second most frequently cited reason is the lack of available labour, either due to a lack of time on the part of farmers or a shortage of service providers to carry out the work. The creation of new digital decision-making tools is not seen as a major lever for improving tree management. A number of people pointed out that the tools exist but are not widely used. There are many reasons for this: lack of time, lack of motivation, apprehension about tools or practices considered too technical, lack of access to tools, unsuitable format, etc. For some, there is even concern about the proliferation of tools, their complexity and the fact that they are evolving too

quickly. Another pitfall pointed out is the failure to take trees into account in the standard farm management tools already used by farmers, or the lack of interaction between the tools produced for trees and other farm management tools.

5. Many resources already exist for tree management.

The interviews and associated research revealed the existence of a large number of resources dedicated to the management of field trees and hedges, some of which are very recent or in the process of being finalised. These resources include digital decision-support tools, especially for agroforestry systems design and species selection. There are not many operational tools for managing the trees, but they include management plans inspired by forestry management plans, which have been in use in France for around twenty years. They are drawn up by agroforestry technicians and advisers for farmers. The sustainable management plans are seen by the stakeholders interviewed as interesting and useful tools for farmers. However, they are considered to be very time-consuming to implement. The resources inventoried include other forms of support for tree management. In fact, virtually all the advisory and support structures we met offer training courses on pruning for farmers, or more generally for managers of trees outside forests. Similarly, many support structures have created their own brochures, and several research or cooperation projects have produced guides and technical sheets that overlap substantially¹. Several databases have been created to bring together scientific and technical resources on agroforestry². A real effort is currently being made to harmonise the tools produced, notably with the creation of a standard national framework for sustainable management plans for hedgerows and agroforestry systems by Chambres d'Agriculture France and Afac-agroforesteries, and the integrated approach to hedgerows promoted by Afac-agroforesteries.

6. The architectural approach is little known among the people interviewed and is not used in current tools.

Although there are many possible applications of the architectural approach in agroforestry, this approach is little known and was not spontaneously mentioned in the tools used. Two interviewees said they had attended a workshop on diagnosing dieback using the ARCHI method (Drénou 2013) and were interested in its application for diagnosing ageing hedges. Some participants were interested in decision-support applications for pruning young trees and renewing trees in older formations. But most of the participants were rather sceptical about the applications of the architectural approach. They feared that the indicators would be too complicated for farmers to handle and would offer nothing more than the indicators already in use.

7. While the proposals to apply the architectural approach in the form of a diagnostic tool to aid decision-making were generally perceived as being too technical, the participants' expectations focused more on improving knowledge of trees through research and passing on this knowledge through training and awareness-raising.

The interviews carried out reveal strong expectations in terms of information and advice on issues related to the functioning of the tree and understanding its reactions to its environment and to management operations. The players interviewed are calling for closer links with research, both to raise their questions and to gain access to the results of research in France, but also more widely in Europe and elsewhere, particularly on the following issues:

¹ AgForward (EU 2014-2017), Transgal (LEADER 2012-2013), and TransAgroForest (LEADER 2017-2021).

² AFINET – Agroforestry Innovation Networks (EU 2017-2020).

- the adaptation of the choice of tree species and planting techniques to increase the resilience of agroforestry systems to climate change,
- the assisted natural regeneration practices,
- the development of tree roots in agroforestry and the reaction of trees to the various operations carried out (root dressing before planting, root banding after planting, tree pruning).

Several of the players interviewed noted that farmers, even those who have undergone training, do not dare prune trees for fear of doing it wrong. They assume that the training courses are too short. One of the participants said that, of the various training courses he offered, the most popular was "Understanding the functioning of a tree" and that he received many requests for other complementary courses, for example on species identification.

With regard to the preferred format for tree management tools, the participants interviewed noted that farmers are very open to digital technology and that the digital format is well suited provided that it adds real value to the content by holding the learners' attention, making them active and energising the learning process. However, several participants stressed the importance of face-to-face and in-the-field exchanges. One interviewee felt that there was a lack of a tool for sharing agroforestry knowledge and practices, such as a collaborative platform.

This is in line with the needs expressed in the DIGITAF Living Labs survey regarding the type of tools requested, except for decision support tools (Table 1).

We therefore propose to mobilise the architectural approach through different knowledge supports to learn how to observe trees and adjust practices according to their condition and potential. To do this, existing materials will be used and supplemented. The whole will be structured to make the information more easily accessible according to the different themes linked to the management of trees in agroforestry. An analysis of the resources available on tree functioning would enable these resources to be structured in relation to the different themes linked to the management of trees in agroforestry. It would also help to identify missing content for which new materials could be created. These could be disseminated via local organisations supporting the development of agroforestry.

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